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Development of integrated innovative techniques for the examination of paintings: the case studies of *The Resurrection of Christ* attributed to Andrea Mantegna and the *Crucifixion of Viterbo* attributed to Michelangelo's workshop

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Abstract

This paper presents the contextual use of Pulse-Compression Thermography and Hypercolorimetric Multispectral Imaging for the diagnostic study of historical heritage paintings. The comparison and the integration of images provided by the two techniques allows the conservation state of both the painting layers and wooden support to be investigated. Relevant information on the painting technique and figurative scene can be obtained as well. The proposed approach was applied to two Italian Renaissance panel paintings. The first object tested was a 16th

century panel painting representing a *Crucifixion*, exposed in the Museum of Colle del Duomo in Viterbo, Italy, and attributed to the workshop of the master Michelangelo Buonarroti. The second artwork was a late 15th century panel painting, representing *The Resurrection of Christ*, currently preserved at Museo Carrara in Bergamo, Italy, and recently re-attributed to Andrea Mantegna; it was identified as being the upper half of a whole composition together with the *Descent into Limbo* painting.

HMI acquisitions and digital image processing tools allowed to investigate the upper painting layer, while PuCT imaging data gave relevant information on the structure of the wooden support proving to be an innovative stratigraphic investigation method. The combination of HMI and PuCT imaging techniques supplied information on the whole structure of the artworks, identifying surface degradation, different layers, wood defects and their position in the inner layers of the object.

The integration of the above-mentioned techniques might stand as a new reference diagnostic method to evaluate conservative needs and support decisions for restoration.

Keywords – panel paintings, pulse compression thermography, hypercolorimetric multispectral imaging, nondestructive diagnostics, Michelangelo Buonarroti, Andrea Mantegna.

1. Introduction

In conservation science and art restoration, non-destructive testing (NDT) techniques have become widely applied due to the necessity of investigating cultural heritage objects, which are fragile, irreplaceable and sometimes impossible to analyze with invasive or destructive methods [1-2]. A valid inspection approach for painting analysis relies on the integration of data collected

from different imaging techniques, combining relative outputs through specific digital imaging processing tools. Imaging data integration can strongly support traditional analytical methods, yielding a comprehensive diagnosis of the painting state of conservation and reducing the ambiguities of information coming from a single diagnostic method [3].

In the present work, an innovative integrated analysis for painting diagnostics that combines InfraRed Thermography (IRT) [4] and Hypercolorimetric Multispectral Imaging (HMI) is proposed [5,6].

1.1 Infrared Thermography

Among the most valuable NDT methods for inspecting cultural heritage objects, IRT currently holds an important place of prominence. InfraRed (IR) and thermal methods are based on the principle that the heat flowing into a Sample Under Test (SUT) is perturbed by the presence of anomalies, such as splitting, voids, etc. These changes in the heat flow cause localized temperature differences detectable onto the material's surface. The imaging or visualization of such thermal imprints by means of a thermal camera, *i.e.*, a camera sensitive to IR radiation, is known as IRT [4,7]. The method allows fast inspections and real-time measurements to be carried out over a given detection area by using suitable lenses. IRT's popularity has grown in recent years due to improvements of thermal cameras that became cheaper, lighter and more accurate.

IRT can be applied both with and without the use of a controlled heat source; the former case is called active IRT, whilst the latter is referred as passive IRT. In passive IRT, the thermal excitation is provided by the environmental conditions (*e.g.*, sun exposure). However, the thermal contrast between defective and non-defective areas is in general low, thus leading to

poor Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR). In addition, experiments cannot be easily reproduced. To improve the sensitivity of passive IRT, advanced image processing techniques were developed, even for the inspection of cultural heritage structures [8]. Nonetheless, the use of an external controlled heat source is in general beneficial to further improve IRT performances, leading to the active IRT. In active IRT, the SUT is assumed being at thermal equilibrium [9], and a heat excitation is applied to reach the desired thermal contrast. The most used active IRT scheme is called Pulsed-Thermography (PT) and it is exploited in a wide range of non-destructive technique applications. PT makes use of high-power flash head lamps (some kJ of energy) for lighting the SUT surface. The same surface is usually monitored by an IR camera. The flash induces a change of the surface temperature causing heat diffusion towards the inner part of the SUT to retrieve thermal equilibrium. An important characteristic of PT is that the flash duration is significantly shorter than the typical heat diffusion time duration within the samples, so that the heating is quasi-instantaneous while the cooling is regulated by the thermal characteristics of the SUT, *i.e.*, specific heat, density and thermal conductivity. The IR camera collects a sequence of thermograms during the cooling process and information concerning the outer and inner part of the SUT can be inferred from the analysis of the cooling trends of each pixel. Precisely, a cooling trend is associated to any pixel of the IR image, which depends on the pixel emissivity but also on the characteristics of the SUT interior structure. If a thermal anomaly is present, a change in the related pixels' temperature decay curves can be observed. From a system-theory perspective, neglecting lateral diffusion [10-11] and non-linear phenomena, the cooling curve $h_{j_x, j_y}(t)$ of the (j_x, j_y) pixel can be considered as its thermal one-dimensional (1D) impulse response where the flash excitation plays the role of the impulsive Dirac delta excitation $\delta(t)$. This assumption has important consequences, since a 1D linear system - as the pixel is assumed

to be - is completely described by its impulse response. PT thus provides a powerful tool to inspect painting allowing: (i) the analysis of the conservation status of paintings [12], (ii) a preliminary characterization of constitutive materials and painting technique [13], (iii) the comparison with additional imaging data [14]. Further, it is possible to distinguish between different SUT depths by analyzing thermograms related to different times of the cooling process. This is possible since layers corresponding to different depths in the SUT will affect the thermal impulse responses at different time instants due to the finite time needed for the heat flow to diffuse from the excited surface towards the interior.

The major potential drawback in applying PT to paintings diagnostic is the risk of provoking thermochromism on the painting surface, as well as the deposition of too high thermal stresses, which may occur if very powerful flashes are used [15]. However, a certain amount of thermal energy must be delivered to the sample to achieve an SNR level that assures the needed sensitivity to detect defects or anomalies.

As a consequence, the main challenge in the application of active IRT to cultural heritage is to reduce the power of the heating system without losing neither the capability of penetration inside the sample nor the sensitivity. The use of coded modulated heating stimuli in combination with pulse-compression, hereafter referred as Pulse-compression Thermography (PuCT) [16] provides a valid aid in this direction. This is because PuCT allows the impulse responses of the pixels to be retrieved even when using long low-power excitations, if some spectral characteristics of the coded signals are assured. Some of the present authors proposed a PuCT scheme based on coded LED excitation capable of optimizing the estimation of the impulse responses compared to the state-of-the-art PuCT literature [17]. The procedure was also tested on mockups realized on both

wooden panel and canvas containing artificially fabricated defects [18]. A further optimized protocol is used here in combination with HMI.

1.2 Hypercolorimetric multispectral imaging

The other technique proposed in this study is the Hypercolorimetric Multispectral Imaging, exploited here following the method and processing developed by Profilocolore Srl [5]. The main advantages of multispectral imaging (MSI) technique in art examination consist of mapping and identifying pigments, binders, restored areas and zones of retouching on the entire surface of the investigated artwork in a non-invasive modality [19-22]. The diagnostic potentialities of MSI can be improved by implementing data processing algorithms for digital images, supporting various aspects of conservation, allowing to observe materials below the surface and, through the combination of different spectral range imaging, to gain latent information on painting technique and old restorations as well as to support artwork authentication [23-24].

Hypercolorimetric multispectral imaging is based on the simultaneous exploitation of the electromagnetic spectrum from the ultraviolet (UV) to the near infrared region of the electromagnetic spectrum [5]. The acquisition, made under a standard metric, allows to characterize the investigated surfaces in a more detailed way than the standard colorimetry. In fact, the classical colorimetry is substituted with a new and wider one resulting in a 7 band colorimetry with functions centered at 350, 450, 550, 650, 750, 850 and 950 nm [5]. The system developed by Profilocolore transforms any spectra in the range 300-1000nm into sevenfold hypercolorimetric coordinates. To reach this, the acquisition procedures starts with a colour target whose spectral reflectance is carefully measured through a laboratory spectroradiometer. The obtained reflectance values are weighed with the Hypercolor Matching Functions and

transformed into 7 hypercolorimetric coordinates. The same target is acquired in imaging mode through the camera in RAW format. In the RAW/Tiff transformation, lens chromatic, spherical geometric and vignetting aberrations and distortions are corrected. The hypercolor profile itself consists of a 7 input/7 output non-linear conversion function automatically synthesized by a Profilcolore proprietary genetic algorithm. The hypercolorimetric coordinates coincide with the continuous spectral reflectance sampled at 350, 450, 550, 650, 750, 850 and 950nm [5]. The achieved result has a great value as it shows how it is possible to obtain a sampled spectral reflectance in imaging mode, *i.e.*, pixel by pixel, and how this is equivalent to an instrumental local measurement [5]. Moreover, further relevant information that are not visible to the naked-eye can be obtained from digital image processing tools. In fact, most interesting findings can be observed by combining different spectral acquisitions and advanced image processing algorithms such as principal component analysis (PCA), pattern recognition, edge detection and cluster analysis. HMI guarantees very high radiometric (better than 95%) and colorimetric precision (better than $\Delta E = 2$) [5]. Taking into account well-established multispectral methods, HMI allows the multispectral channels to be effectively combined due to the calibrated data obtained after the acquisition through a modified camera. Indeed, it has been shown in [5] that the possibility of combining the multispectral channels after calibration provides great advantages in terms of information amount that can be extracted from the acquired data. Another great advantage of HMI is the short time needed for the acquisition - only three shots are needed - without the necessity of any power supply [5], thus providing great advantages in artworks examination, especially during *in-situ* investigations.

In the present work, the two techniques were tested on two Italian Renaissance panel paintings having not only great historical and artistic values, but also peculiar stories. The first artwork

tested was a 16th century oil on panel painting representing a *Crucifixion* attributed to Michelangelo's workshop [25] and currently on display in the Museum of Colle del Duomo in Viterbo, Italy (Fig.1A). Previous investigations, based on traditional photographic and spectroscopic techniques, highlighted interesting details in the *Crucifixion* painting that deserved further deepening, such as the technique used to draw the St. John face [25]. The face, in fact, changes its traits when observed under UV fluorescence assuming a more masculine appearance. Another interesting detail concerns the face of Christ that appears dark and seems re-painted from the rest of the figure. Lastly, the Magdalene at the foot of the cross seems to be added subsequently both to the Virgin and the cross, leading to the hypothesis that it was added subsequently to the other parts of the painting. Art historians hypothesized that the change in Christ face and the probable addition of Magdalene could be linked to the 1556 catholic reforming decree of the Pope Paul IV (born Gian Pietro Carafa), that established some dictates in religious painting representations such as that forbidding to depict the crucified Christ alive [26]. The second artwork inspected was *The Resurrection of Christ*, a late 15th century (about 1492) tempera on panel painting owned by the Accademia Carrara, Bergamo, Italy (Fig.1B). In May 2018, this painting was re-attributed to Andrea Mantegna by Dr. Giovanni Valagussa, who identified it as the upper half of a unique composition, whose lower part is the *Descent into Limbo* painting [27]. The dismembering of famous paintings was a well-known and frequent practice since the Renaissance, with the purpose to gain more in a sale but also to adapt the artworks to customer's demands [28].

Beyond the main lengthwise cut, *The Resurrection* underwent other further modifications as the added of a 2-cm-wide board of walnut wood on the left edge of the panel in a restoration of late 16th – early 17th century [27]. In this new appearance, the painting was bought by Guglielmo

Lochis in 1846 before entering the Accademia Carrara collection in 1866, where -probably after some bad restorations suffered in those 20 years- it was at that time downgraded as a copy of Andrea Mantegna, maybe made by his son Francesco Mantegna [27].

At the time of the experimental activities reported here, *The Resurrection of Christ* was being restored at the Accademia Carrara by Ms. Delfina Fagnani Sesti.

The main aims for applying the two techniques on the panel paintings can be summarize as follows: i) to investigate the general conservation status of both artworks in order to support the restoration work, underway in the case of *The Resurrection of Christ*, and to be carried out in the near future in the case of the *Crucifixion*; ii) to detect details of the painting layers, of the ground and of the wood support such as areas of ancient retouching and re-paintings, grouting, preparatory drawing, wood defects, nails, cracks, etc.; iii) to make hypothesis about pigment composition; iv) to reveal details in the paintings' construction that could help to support the artworks attribution. In fact, especially for the *Crucifixion* panel painting, the attribution to Michelangelo Buonarroti workshop is still under discussion between art historians and the information derived from the present investigation can be particularly useful for the discussion [29].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 PuCT theoretical base and experimental setup

As mentioned, active IRT aims at characterizing the impulse responses associated to the pixel of the thermograms for extracting useful information about the SUT. In painting examinations, this goal should be achieved by using low-power heat stimuli, so as to prevent possible alterations or damages of the artworks. Note that the commonly used approach of lowering the heat power

while increasing the excitation time is not the optimal one. In fact, the single pixel signal would be no longer a good approximation of the impulse-response if the excitation pulse is too long. Such incorrect procedure makes difficult to interpret data, even if it increases the SNR for some defects [30]. The physical reason underlying this aspect is that by extending the pulse duration, the frequency content of the excitation signal is compressed to low-frequencies, thus reducing the information content of the thermograms sequence. This is a crucial point and it is worth giving more insight. Suppose that a heat source is modulated by a sinusoidal signal at frequency f [Hz]. How much is it possible to penetrate/inspect within the sample with such excitation? Moreover, which is the spatial resolution achievable? The answer to both these questions is provided by the definition of the thermal diffusion length μ , which is the characteristic distance from the SUT surface at which the heat flow amplitude is decreased by a factor $e \approx 2.71$ with respect to its initial amplitude. Further, the parameter μ is also related to the depth resolution achievable at a given inspection frequency. The quantity μ depends on the sample physical characteristics and on the modulation frequency, according to expression (1):

$$\mu = \sqrt{\frac{\alpha}{\pi f}} \text{ [m]} \quad (1)$$

in which $\alpha = \frac{k}{c\rho} \text{ [}\frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{s}}\text{]}$ is the thermal diffusivity. Here, $c \text{ [}\frac{\text{J}}{\text{kg}\cdot\text{K}}\text{]}$ is the specific heat, $\rho \text{ [}\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}\text{]}$ is the density, and $k \text{ [}\frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}\cdot\text{K}}\text{]}$ is the thermal conductivity. The higher is f , the smaller is the inspection depth achievable but the higher is the depth resolution. A range of frequencies/thermal diffusion lengths must be therefore excited contextually to assure both a good sensitivity of inspection for all the layers of interest in a painting (varnish, paint, drawing, canvas or wooden support, etc.), and a spatial resolution capable of separating thinner surface layers from thicker inner ones. In addition, a certain SNR value - which is also frequency dependent - must be achieved for all the

inspection depth/frequency range. PT accomplishes this goal by using a very short excitation pulse that excites a wide range of frequencies but, if the peak power of the pulse is reduced, the delivered energy is too small to assure a good SNR, especially at low frequencies/high inspection depths.

PuCT instead modulates a low-power heat source by means of a coded waveform, which can be designed to cope with a wanted excitation spectrum. As a result, the energy is delivered to the SUT spread both in time and in frequency, assuring a great flexibility in the measurement procedure and making possible the use of low power sources. To better understand the proposed approach, it is useful to compare graphically the PT and the PuCT techniques, as shown in Fig. 2 [17].

In PT (Fig. 2a), the excitation is considered instantaneous and the sample impulse thermal response is measured for a time T_h , which is the expected duration of the impulse response of interest, *i.e.*, the time necessary for the heat diffusion and to retrieving a new thermal equilibrium. In PuCT (Fig. 2b), the sample is excited with a coded excitation of duration T , while the thermograms are collected for a time $(T + T_h)$ [31-32]. By applying the Pulse Compression (PuC) algorithm, an estimated impulse thermal response of duration T_h can be retrieved. A thorough description of the PuC theory lies beyond the scope of this article and the reader is referred to the literature on the topic, see for instance [17, 33-38]. Here, only the main steps of the PuCT are summarized and illustrated in Fig. 2b.

A coded excitation $s(t)$ is provided along with the so-called matched filter $\Psi(t)$ such that their convolution, here represented by the symbol “*”, approximates the Dirac’s Delta function: $s(t) * \Psi(t) \approx \delta(t)$.

$s(t)$ excites the SUT that outputs the signal $y(t) = h(t) * s(t)$. By exploiting the properties of linear systems, an estimate of $h(t)$ is retrieved by convolving the system output $y(t)$ with $\Psi(t)$:

$$y(t) * \Psi(t) = (h(t) * s(t)) * \Psi(t) = h(t) * (s(t) * \Psi(t)) \approx h(t) * \delta(t) \approx h(t) \quad (2)$$

Many possible choices of the pair $\{s(t), \Psi(t)\}$ were proposed in literature and applied also to PuCT (Barker codes [14-15], linear and non-linear chirp signals [18, 31-33, 39]). In all the cases, $\Psi(t) = s(-t)$ maximizes the SNR but could not be optimal in term of fidelity in the reconstruction of the $h(t)$'s, which is very important in paintings inspection due to the complexity of the SUT. Moreover, after the application of PuC, some further processing must be implemented, such as the selection of the time interval of interest by removing the first T seconds of the PuC output, as shown in Fig. 2b. However, beside these technical considerations, here it is worth to highlight two physical aspects that differentiate PuCT from other PuC applications: (i) the difficulty in realizing a bipolar heat source and (ii) the need to distribute, in a reasonable measurement time, the excitation energy in a frequency band wide enough for ensuring contextually both sensitivity to hidden defects and high time-resolution in the $h(t)$ estimation. The first issue was successfully tackled in [17] where it was shown how to optimally apply PuC while using unipolar heat sources. To solve the second point, in the present work a pseudo-noise (PN) Legendre code was used as $s(t)$ [35], and the PuC scheme described in [36-37] was adopted.

PN codes are sequences of 1's and 0's with randomness properties that make them appear noise-like even if generated by deterministic algorithms. Legendre's sequences are a family of PN constructed from Legendre symbol (x/p) , which is a short hand notation for expressing whether "x" is a quadratic residue modulo p or not, where p must be intended as a prime number. With respect to Barker and chirp based PuCT protocols, the present one relying on Legendre

sequences provides a better estimation of the $h(t)$'s, allowing the full exploitation of the PT powerful analysis. The experimental setup used to implement the PuCT procedure is the same used in [17-18, 32] and illustrated in Fig. 2c.

In particular, the signal generation/acquisition was managed by LabviewTM software.

Thermograms were collected through a Xenics Onca-MWIR (3.6–4.9 μ m)-InSb camera placed in reflection mode, having a resolution of 320 \times 240 pixels, connected to a NI-1433 Camera Link Frame Grabber. The distance between the painting and the camera was between 50 and 100 cm. Eight LED chips emitting in the visible spectrum were used as heat source with an operating total power of \sim 110 W. The coded excitation driving the LEDs was provided by a TDK Lambda GEN 750W power supply. The frame grabber and the power supply were synchronously driven by the signals provided by a National Instrument PCI-6711 Arbitrary Waveform Generation (AWG) board. Both the AWG board and the grabber were connected to a central PC/DSP Unit. Before applying PuCT to the paintings, some tests were performed on mockups to evaluate painting materials stability for the employed heating scheme (see Supplementary file).

2.2 HMI: SpectralPick[®] acquisition and calibration

The HMI system consists of two main tools, *i.e.*, a SpectraPick for the image acquisition and a calibration system and PickViewer software for the image analysis. The SpectraPick system is based on the use of an optimized set of imaging sensors, optical filters, radiometric references, natural light or xenon flashes, and a calibration software.

HMI acquisition was performed through a Nikon D810FR 36 Megapixel camera, modified to obtain full-range spectral reflectance measurements of the SUT surface, as showed in detail in previous works [5, 6, 40]. The camera is equipped with interchangeable lenses to adapt over

distance and dimensions of the SUT, and with two multiband pass filters with spectral transmittances that are sufficiently complementary. By combining the filters with the Bayer filters of the modified camera sensor, the camera can correctly sample the whole 300-1000 nm range.

The lighting plays a key role and needs to span the whole wavelength range 300-1000 nm with no missing frequencies. To this aim, xenon flashes were chosen among different possible solutions. In particular, Nikon SB910 flashes were used after removing their front plastic lenses, thus allowing also the UV wavelength to be emitted. The UV induced fluorescence (UVF) was then obtained by filtering the flashes light with a UV band pass filter with a cut at 380 nm, and UV-IR cut filter (400-700 nm) in front of the camera. As previously mentioned, a calibration step is needed before proceeding with HMI measurement. To this aim, the radiometric references consisted of a number of white patches surrounding the object and of 36 patches colour-checkers built using colour samples from the NCS – Natural Colour System®© catalog. The spectral reflectance of the references was accurately measured in the range 220-1050 nm in Proficolore laboratory, with 0.7 nm accuracy (Instrument System Spectroradiometer CAS 140 CT and dark room).

The calibration procedure is executed by: 1) analyzing the white patches to achieve correct white balance and even exposure; 2) running an artificial intelligence based optimizer that finds the mathematical functions to relate camera digital values of the colour-checker into radiometric and colorimetric measurements; 3) applying the calibration to the acquired images and producing seven monochromatic images, 16 bit TIFF format, containing the spectral reflectance values at 350, 450, 550, 650 (hereinafter referred as VIS), 750, 850 and 950 nm (hereinafter referred as IR1, IR2, IR3 respectively), and a single AdobeRGB TIFF 16 bit colour image. The achieved

precision across the whole 36 megapixels image is higher than 95% on the spectral reflectance images and colour error less than CIE2000 $\Delta E=2$ for the colour image [40].

The whole calibration and alignment process requires few minutes and can be performed *in situ* for an immediate results analysis.

2.3 HMI: PickViewer® processor

After the image acquisition and calibration processing, carried out using SpectraPick®, the multispectral images were processed through the HMI software PickViewer®, developed by Profilocolore. The PickViewer software provides powerful image processing tools able to reveal and achieve relevant information. It further allows gathering information on hidden data from the images acquired with SpectraPick system, containing spectral reflectance and colour coordinates for each of the 36 megapixels of the captured scene. Data are calibrated and are absolute, depending only on the spectral characteristics of the surface.

Several kinds of analyses are possible with PickViewer, such as: add and integrate any other imaging data (fluorescence, X-ray, thermal etc.); multichannel images viewer; any pixel colorimetry and spectral reflectance read-out; mapping by: colour, spectra, arbitrary channels; principal components analysis; contrast enhancement through digital imaging processing algorithms as NDVI (normalized difference vegetative index); neural network based clustering; colour and spectral signature database; two ways mapping by database entry; any channel to RGB false colours visualization; channels math, indexes and normalised contrast; calibration and colour-checker test.

Each relevant result can be saved as image in tiff, png or jpeg format. Results saved in tiff format can be reloaded as further derived channels and used combined with all the others [5].

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 PuCT

The PuCT output consists in a time- sequence of images where the time evolution of the (j_x, j_y) pixel intensity is nothing but its thermal impulse response $h_{j_x, j_y}(t)$. By analyzing images at different cooling times, it is possible to clearly appreciate the upper painting layer and the wood inner structure of the support in the same acquisition, permitting a non-invasive stratigraphic analysis of the painting. This is illustrated in Fig. 3 for the *Crucifixion*, wherein acquisitions were made on the whole figure and also by zooming onto the Christ's figure. At the beginning ($t_{cooling} \leq 0.5s$) only the paint layer affects the surface emissivity, so the thermal image is strictly correlated with the visible one (lighter colours appear colder than darker ones). As the cooling proceeds, the surface emissivity is affected also by the wood grain of the underlying panel. After few seconds ($t_{cooling} \geq 4s$), the contribute of the paint layer to the thermal image is almost null while the deep structure of the wood panel is visualized.

The same analysis was also executed on Mantegna's painting *The Resurrection of Christ* and results are depicted in Fig. 4, showing both Christ's figure and the top-right part of the painting. Even in this case, only the paint layer affects the surface emissivity at the beginning of the cooling stage. However, the surface emissivity starts to be affected also by the wood grain of the underlying panel as time elapses, *i.e.* as the cooling takes place. In addition, quite regular horizontal lines are visible for $0.25s \leq t_{cooling} \leq 0.5s$, especially on the top-right part, which should be located just underneath the paint layer and over the wooden support. The horizontal lines are very regular - they have the same height and are equidistant. This led the authors to suppose that the horizontal lines might be related to the application of the gypsum and glue

preparatory layer in coatings, as described by the Medieval artist Cennino Cennini in his technical essay, where he recommended to finish the preparatory layer with up to eight thin gypsum coatings, alternating vertical and horizontal brushstrokes [41].

It's worth noting that only few frames are shown here, but any other time interval of the sequence can be willfully chosen, enabling the examination of a high and changeable number of investigated layers: this is a significant advantage when inspecting complex objects like those of cultural heritage. To the best of the authors' knowledge, such results are not achievable with other diagnostic imaging techniques, but only when combining different methods from different sources, though no real imaging integration is often possible. Further, in this case at different times correspond different thermal images, which can be correlated to different depths within the SUT. In addition, PuCT analysis can also consider different features than just emissivity for imaging purposes. For instance, time-phase was introduced in [31, 33] in combination with PuCT. Time-phase is a feature extracted from pixel impulse response and it is expected to be almost independent from the pixel emissivity, hence from the colour. Fig. 5 shows the images of four areas of *The Resurrection of Christ* obtained by visualizing both emissivity (left) and time-phase (right) features at $t_{cooling} = 0s$. Time-phase allows a direct visualization of the wood grain of the panel and in general of the structure behind the paint layer.

Besides these imaging capabilities, the analysis of PuCT images also confirmed some facts or hypotheses on specific details of both paintings.

In fact, PuCT confirmed alterations in Christ's face in the *Crucifixion*, since the pictorial layer presents significant differences in the thermographic response (shown in grayscale in terms of thermal emissivity as a darker area) in comparison to the body.

In *The Resurrection of Christ*, PuCT images reported in Fig. 6, bottom-left quadrant, highlight the presence of two nails and the related grouting. A long crack is also visible in correspondence of one nail underneath the lying down figure. To better highlight these details, Fig. 6 reports a sequence of images of the bottom-left-quadrant corresponding to different cooling times that illustrate how, in the case of the nails, firstly is detected the grouting as a hot spot. Then, the section of the nails appears as a cold spot as time elapses, due to the higher thermal conductivity of metal with respect to the background. Regarding the crack, the authors assume this is the case since the wood grain pattern, which is well visible, has a different direction around the crack. As a curiosity, by comparing emissivity and time-phase images reported in Fig. 5, it is possible to notice that the mountain shape on the background of the Christ figure follows the pattern of the wood grains underneath.

Starting from these results, many image and signal processing techniques could be applied to the thermal images. As a starting point, in this paper the PuCT results are integrated with those from HMI, as explained in the next subsection.

3.1 HMI

As explained in the previous Section, HMI allows several image processing possibilities that can be performed on the calibrated multispectral images. In the present discussion, the most relevant images and their combinations will be shown. The UVF images obtained through HMI (Fig. 7) clearly show the conservation condition of the entire painting surface of the two paintings examined, highlighting areas repaired (dark colour) and abrasions.

In the *Crucifixion* (Fig. 7a) UVF highlighted three main vertical cracks in the painting layers in correspondence of ancient repairs of the wooden support. Some areas seem to exhibit bright red

fluorescence (Christ's perizoma and St. John's garment), suggesting the possible presence of organic lakes. UVF image also reveals a detail (Fig. 8b) of St. John's face appearing different from what is seen in the visible (Fig. 8a). In particular, it assumes more masculine traits and a hollowed aspect, the neck appears slim and the hair hung loose on the shoulder respect to its aspect, more graceful, round and feminine in the visible radiation. The singularity of this difference is that it is present only in the face of St. John and so it appears intentional, as previously discussed also in relation to the historical background [25-26]. The hypothesis of art historians is that the painting should be observed with glass, lamp and mirror in order to see the changes in Saint John face, according to the letter "*del lume*" (of the lamp) that Vittoria Colonna wrote to Michelangelo about a *Crucifixion*. The possible relation of the letter to the *Crucifixion* is reported by Antonio Rocca, an art historian of Egidio17, in his book [26, pag. 53]. The friendship of Michelangelo with Vittoria Colonna, and consequently with the *Ecclesia Viterbensis* is well-documented in literature and most certainly influenced his artistic thought and production, as reported in the literature [42-44].

At the present state of restoration, the UVF image (Fig. 7b) of *The Resurrection of Christ* allows the upper varnishing layer over the figure of Christ to be clearly noticed -still not cleaned by the restorer - and to appreciate a vertical discontinuity in the varnish coats on Christ's torso, which could probably be due to different applications of varnishes in different periods.

Other worth-mentioning DIP outputs were obtained applying contrast enhancement on IR3 and the first principal component resulting from PCA run on the UVF image of the *Crucifixion* (Fig. 9a). This processing highlighted general structural damages and discontinuities especially in the left part of the painting. Three main vertical cracks in the painting layers are visible in correspondence of ancient repairs of the wood support. The area corresponding to the vertical

crack is darker with respect to the background, suggesting that it was filled by stucco, during the previous mentioned restoration, and retouched. The garment of Magdalene at the foot of the cross overlays with the Virgin's mantle, supporting art historian studies [25-26] according to which the Magdalene is a later addition, due to the garment typology that can be dated back to the '60s of the 16th century (private communication made by Elisabetta Gnignera, art historian and specialist of Renaissance costume).

A detail of PCA first principal component (PC1) achieved by analyzing IR1, IR2 and IR3 information in correspondence of Christ's torso, highlights the complete disappearing of the wound that instead is well-shown in the visible image (Fig. 10). This could be due to a later addition of the wound or to the wound being realized with pigments transparent to the IR radiation. In Fig. 10 the face of Christ appears, in the visible, darker and roughed out with respect to rest of the body. In addition, it seems a smoother layer compared with the surrounding background of the painting. HMI investigation confirmed this observation showing that Christ's face has a different spectral response with respect to the rest of the figure, suggesting that this area had been abraded or heavily retouched in previous restorations. It is out of the scope of this paper to explain why the Christ face was abraded and repainted, but art historians could use this datum to make connection with the historical period to which the painting seems to be referred, *i.e.*, the first half of 16th century.

PCA gave relevant results also in *The Resurrection of Christ* painting, allowing to appreciate the very good conservation state of the panel, with no discontinuities in the pictorial layer. This result confirms the impression of the restorer after the initial phases of cleaning procedures when it immediately appeared clear the excellent state of preservation as well as the high quality of the painting technique (Fig.9b) [27].

Additional digital image processing (DIP) tools such as false-colour IR image (Fig. 11) and false-colour UV image (Fig. 12) enables to make hypothesis on pigments' typology in the palette of Andrea Mantegna, based on their different spectral reflectance. In IR channels false colour, blue areas become vinous red and the red ones appear as intense yellow. The orange zones assume a light yellow colour. The UV images supply other information concerning the painted areas. Specifically, the red and orange parts, which appear yellow in IR false-colour, have different colours under UV, *i.e.*, the red paint becomes violet whereas the orange one transforms into purple colour. The blue paint used for the sky and parts of the clothing becomes green in UV false-colour, suggesting that the same blue pigment was used.

By combining these findings, it can be supposed that the artist used ultramarine blue for the blue areas, vermilion/cinnabar for the red ones, and red lead for the orange parts.

Furthermore, in the false-colour UV image two different spectral responses are observed in the garment of the soldier on the left, suggesting the use of two different yellow pigments, the first one original, while the second used in an ancient restoration. This datum is in accordance with the addition of the wooden 2-cm board on the left that completed the missing details also with some arbitrary choices, such as the head of the soldier on the left which pertains to another figure in the background. This result is based on the existence of an ancient copy, probably by Girolamo Mocetto (Venetian school, 1458-1531), that showed the original version of Mantegna's *Resurrection* as it appeared in the Gonzaga inventory of 1627 [27, 45].

Further statistical processing was done through normalized difference of HMI UVF, UV and images in the visible spectrum, which allowed to appreciate details in the rock background whose finest design was not visible before (Fig. 13). A clear shift can also be observed in the position of Christ's right arm, probably due to a *pentimento* of the artist.

3.3 Integration of HMI and PuCT

The most interesting results were obtained by combining HMI and PuCT imaging results in Profilocolore PickViewer® software. DIP of multispectral and thermographic data allowed the pictorial surface characteristics and the natural structure of the wooden support to be deeply correlated. This was achieved by applying PCA on HMI UV-induced fluorescence images and on PuCT images at different cooling times. The vertical cracks of the panel - restored with stucco during an ancient intervention – running across the right branch of the cross in the *Crucifixion*, appear perfectly related and coherent with the underlying wood grain, as shown in the second principal component (Fig. 14a). In the second principal component matching HMI UVF and PuCT only at 0.22 s and 0.84 s (deeper layer in the support), a wood knot is clearly visible in correspondence with Christ's right arm (Fig. 14b).

For *The Resurrection of Christ*, DIP tools as Normalized Difference applied to PuCT and IR images (Fig. 15a) stressed the high correlation between the paint layer and the wooden support. In fact, the painting composition seems to follow the wood grain underneath as also shown in the PCA results on PuCT detail of Christ figure (Fig. 15b), that is centered in the area of the wood knot. This could probably be due to the very thin gypsum preparation that Mantegna used and which has been esteemed to have a thickness of around 10 µm [46-47]; such a thin layer allows the natural wood grain of the panel to be seen - Mantegna could have potentially used them as a spatial reference for the realization of the painted scene.

Finally, it must be mentioned that, due to its high value and importance, Andrea Mantegna's painting was investigated with traditional diagnostic techniques including X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF), infrared (IR), false colour infrared (IRC) and ultraviolet (UV) photography,

and digital optical imaging used in clinical healthcare as computed axial tomography (CAT) and Digital Breast Tomosynthesis (DBT). The data from these techniques has not yet been published, but they have been useful during the restoration of the painting. Nonetheless, the integration of HMI and PuCT enabled to obtain all the valuable information achieved through numerous traditional methods, which require normally longer time and higher costs. Furthermore, the combined use of HMI and PuCT allows to gather several further details by applying only two imaging techniques that are rapid, contactless and specifically optimized for painting materials analysis. The use of HMI and PuCT cannot completely replace methods based on spectroscopy, such as XRF and micro-Raman, but certainly may substitute photographic techniques often realized through more than one camera, e.g., reflectography and ultraviolet photography. HMI, in fact, makes it possible to obtain UV, visible and IR calibrated high resolution images with a single acquisition system in a rapid and reproducible way. PuCT is able to perform a stratigraphic investigation of the painting and to reveal defects, discontinuities, cracks, inclusions of foreign materials, and so on, through a rapid non-invasive and portable apparatus. The obtained images, at different cooling times, allow for observing layer by layer the structure of the painting.

4. Conclusions

This work demonstrated how new non-invasive imaging techniques, *i.e.*, Hypercolorimetric Multispectral Imaging (HMI) and Pulse Compression Thermography (PuCT), and their combined integration can supply valid and useful information on ancient paintings, especially to map the conservation condition and to reveal invisible details useful for possible restoration works and for painting attributions, respectively.

The paintings under investigation are a *Crucifixion*, attributed to Michelangelo Buonarroti workshop and exposed in the Museum of Colle del Duomo of Viterbo (Central Italy), and *The Resurrection of Christ* recently attributed to Andrea Mantegna and exposed in the Accademia Carrara of Bergamo (Italy).

In the analysis of both paintings, HMI acquisitions and digital image processing tools allowed to investigate the upper painting layer, while PuCT imaging data gave relevant information on the structure of the wooden support proving to be an innovative stratigraphic investigation method.

In both investigated artworks, the combined use of HMI and PuCT gave interesting results, highlighting aspects concerning the state of conservation and painting techniques. The techniques were useful during the restoration of *The Resurrection of Christ*, while they will help the conservators in the case of *Crucifixion* whose restoration is about to begin.

PuCT analysis revealed the presence of very regular horizontal lines under the painting layers in *The Resurrection* that can be related to the application of the gypsum and glue ground layers, as described by the medieval artist Cennino Cennini in his technical essay. PuCT images further highlighted the presence of two nails, the related grouting, and a long crack. An interesting detail revealed by PuCT is that the mountain shape on the background of the Christ figure follows the pattern of the wood grains underneath.

In the *Crucifixion* panel painting, PuCT confirmed alterations in Christ's face, since the pictorial layer presents significant differences in the thermographic response in comparison to the body.

This result supports the hypothesis of the art historian that the Christ' face was abraded and badly re-painted.

HMI analysis on *The Resurrection of Christ* painting, allowed to appreciate the very good conservation state of the panel, with no discontinuities in the pictorial layer. IR false-colour and

UV false-colour images led to suppose that the artist used ultramarine blue for the blue areas, vermilion/cinnabar for the red ones and red lead for the orange parts. HMI further highlighted the different responses of materials in the original and added parts of the panel painting, particularly evident on the left side.

The main results of HMI on the *Crucifixion* concerns the conservation status, affected by several retouches and three main vertical cracks. HMI images also confirmed the singularity of St. John face that changes its aspect if observed under UV in respect to the visible. Also in this case the analysis supports the hypothesis of the art historians who suppose that the painting should be observed through a glass, a mirror and a lamp, according the letter “*del lume*” (of the lamp) that Vittoria Colonna wrote to Michelangelo.

Another important result concerns the figure of Magdalene at the foot of the cross that was definitely confirmed to be a later addition, as it overlaps the Virgin’s mantle. HMI also highlighted that the face of Christ has a different spectral response with respect to the rest of the figure, suggesting that this area had been abraded or heavily retouched in previous restorations.

In the case of the *The Resurrection of Christ*, HMI allows the upper varnishing layer over the figure of Christ to be clearly noticed -still not cleaned by the restorer - and to appreciate a vertical discontinuity in the varnish coats on Christ’s torso, which could probably be due to different applications of varnishes in different periods.

The combination of HMI and PuCT imaging results in Profilocolore PickViewer® software allowed to highlight further details in the inspected paintings.

Specifically, for *The Resurrection of Christ*, high correlation between the paint layer and the wooden support was revealed. In fact, the painting composition seems to follow the wood grain underneath as also shown in the PCA results on PuCT detail of Christ figure centered in the area

of the wood knot. On the one hand, this could probably be due to the very thin gypsum preparation that Mantegna used and which has been evaluated to have a thickness of around 10 μm ; such a thin layer allows the natural wood grain of the panel to be seen. On the other hand, Mantegna could have potentially used them as a spatial reference for the realization of the painted scene.

In the case of *Crucifixion*, the combined use of HMI and PuCT showed that the vertical cracks of the panel - restored with stucco during an ancient intervention – running across the right branch of the cross in the Crucifixion, appear perfectly related and coherent with the underlying wood grain.

In this first applications on ancient paintings, the combination of HMI and PuCT imaging techniques appears as a convincing and promising non-invasive diagnostic technique to investigate the whole structure of the artwork *in-situ*, identifying surface degradation, different layers, wood defects and their position in the inner layers of the object.

Moreover, the detailed mapping of the conservation state of the painting will be particularly relevant for its future restoration project that is going to start.

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(A)

(B)

Figure 1. (A) *Crucifixion*, oil on panel painting, Museo del Colle del Duomo, Viterbo, Italy, attributed to the Michelangelo's workshop; (B) *The Resurrection of Christ* during restoration at the time of the measurements, tempera on panel, Accademia Carrara, Bergamo, Italy, attributed to Andrea Mantegna, ca. 1492.

Figure 2. (a) Pulsed Thermography (PT) measurement scheme; (b) Pulse-Compression Thermography (PuCT) measurement scheme; (c) sketch of the PuCT experimental setup. The AWG board provided a clock signal for the frame grabber at which the Xenics Onca-MWIR-InSb IR camera is connected, and it provide also the input signal for the LED power supply. The LED driving current waveform is therefore synchronized with the camera frame grabber.

Figure 3. (a) *Crucifixion*, images of thermographic emissivity retrieved after PuCT at different cooling times;(b) zoom on the Christ's figure. The details of wood panel become clearly visible after 1s of cooling while the influence of the paint texture becomes negligible after 2s of cooling.

Figure 4. *The Resurrection of Christ*, images of thermographic emissivity retrieved after PuCT at different cooling times. The details of wood panel become clearly visible after 1s of cooling while the influence of the paint texture become negligible after 2s of cooling for (a) Christ's figure and (b) Christ's body.

Figure 5. *The Resurrection of Christ*, comparison between PuCT images of the thermographic emissivity (left) and time-phase (right) features in partially overlapping painting areas.

Figure 6. *The Resurrection of Christ*, comparison among PuCT images of the bottom-left-quadrant corresponding to different cooling times, showing the grouting, nails and cracks.

Figure 7. (a) HMI UVF image of the *Crucifixion* panel painting; (b) HMI UVF image of *The Resurrection of Christ* by Andrea Mantegna, highlighting areas with residual varnish during the cleaning procedure.

Figure 8. Comparison of the detail and detail of St. John's face in the *Crucifixion* in HMI VIS (a) and HMI UVF image (b).

Figure 9. (a) Results of HMI processing output of contrast enhancement (NDVI) on IR3 and first PC of PCA on UVF of the *Crucifixion* showing the fractures and the restored areas; (b) results of PCA applied on IR1 -IR2 -IR3 digital images of *The Resurrection of Christ*: first principal component of PCA that highlights the painting areas still covered by the varnish and the general good state of conservation of the panel.

Fig. 10. Detail of PC1 applied on IR1 -IR2 -IR3 digital images showing the Christ' wound not visible in the infrared image.

Fig. 11. False- colour IR image of *The Resurrection of Christ* shown in PickViewer GUI.

Fig. 12. False- colour UV image of *The Resurrection of Christ* showed in PickViewer GUI.

Fig. 13. Normalized difference of HMI UVF, UV and VIS images applied via Spectrapick software.

Fig.14. (a) Second principal component from PCA on HMI UVF and PuCT at 0.017s, 0.22s, 0.84s and 1.85s as shown in the PickViewer software interface. (b) Second principal component from PCA on HMI UVF and PuCT at 0.22 s, and 0.84 s as shown in the PickViewer software interface

Fig.15. Details of the output of HMI and PuCT integration. (a) Normalized Difference on PuCT and HMI IR shows how wood grains are visible through the upper pictorial layer. (b) PCA applied over PuCT data shows the panel support in the same investigated area.